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EVIDENCE SUPPORT ITS EXISTENCE?

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The Critical Period Hypothesis for L2 Acquisition: Does the Evidence Support its Existence?

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Abstract: In this essay, I explore the Critical Period Hypothesis (CPH) in language acquisition, which suggests the existence of a specific time frame during which humans can achieve native-like fluency in a second language (L2). I begin with a historical overview highlighting the methodological issues and criticism of statistical analysis in CPH studies. I mention two contemporary studies, Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021), which I posit to be good examples of how to respond to statistical critiques. I discuss critiques of CPH research methodology, focusing on issues such as the lack of a clear definition for the critical period (CP), variations in experimental designs, and the effects of the native language on second language acquisition. I propose a hypothesis linking the CP to the development of logical thinking in children and suggest using neuroimaging techniques, i.e., ERP and fMRI, to investigate this connection, drawing on proposals by Krashen (1975) and Rosansky (1975) to connect CPH with the theories of Inhelder & Piaget (1958). In summary, the CPH for language acquisition remains a topic of debate, but recent studies have provided stronger statistical support. I encourage continued research to better understand the CP and its relationship with cognitive development.

Plain English Abstract: This paper discusses the Critical Period hypothesis for second language acquisition, which suggests the existence of a period in which an individual must be exposed to a language to achieve native-like fluency, after which it is no longer possible. In this paper, I give an overview of the hypothesis from its beginnings with Lenneberg's research on patients with the language-related disorder aphasia in 1967. I detail the methodological challenges of critical period research, including finding an adequate statistical model to analyse the data, and the subsequent improvements by more contemporary studies, such as those conducted by Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021). As these methodological challenges are being overcome, there is more support than ever before for the hypothesis. I argue that the hypothesis is well-supported by the data. Then, I suggest a cognitive mechanism that has been speculated by previous researchers Krashen (1975) and Rosansky (1975). These two researchers hypothesised that the third stage of the development of logical thought in children is linked to the critical period. I suggest an experimental design using neuroimaging, including fMRI and EEG, that might find evidence of such a link. I conclude by encouraging continued research to better understand the CP and its relationship with cognitive development.

Keywords: Critical Period Hypothesis; Second Language Acquisition; ultimate attainment; learning ability; learning rate; aptitude

1 Introduction

Adult learners rarely achieve levels of L2 ultimate attainment (UA), defined as the peak language development that a speaker attains in their lifetime, equivalent to the UA of those who acquired their L2 as children. Although adult learners outperform children in immersion settings during the initial months (Krashen et al., 1979), children have a long-term advantage in L2 acquisition. The Critical Period Hypothesis (CPH) for language acquisition has been an explanation for this phenomenon. Critical periods (CP) are spans of time in an organism's development when it must acquire a specific capacity, after which it can no longer do so. The CPH posits that there is a CP for the human capacity to acquire language, after which a speaker can no longer reach native-like levels of fluency.

Lenneberg (1967) first formulated the CPH, predicting that language acquisition occurs most efficiently between infancy and puberty. Later research on the CPH suggested that the CP affects L2 acquisition. The CP and its effects on L2 acquisition have been tested, but methodological issues have sown doubt about the validity of experimental results of CPH studies (Hakuta & Bialystok, 1994; Vanhove, 2013). Singleton & Leśniewska (2021, p. 2) posit that the CPH ‘remains unproven but also unfalsified’.

In this essay, I examine CPH literature and argue that contemporary research (Hartshorne et al., 2018; Chen & Hartshorne, 2021) has provided rigorous statistical analysis and that CPH research has strong supporting evidence. Then, in Section 6, I suggest future research to test a potential link between the CPH and the development of logical thinking (DLT) in children.

2 Origin of the critical period hypothesis

2.1 Lenneberg (1967)

Lenneberg (1967) introduced the CPH in the publication *Biological Foundations of Language*, in which he examines converging evidence from language recovery in aphasia patients of different ages, language development (LD) in individuals with Down Syndrome (DS), and the effects of acquired deafness on LD. He hypothesised that the cause of the CP was the onset of cerebral lateralisation, a period in neurological development when neuroplasticity reduces and assigns fixed cognitive functions to each brain hemisphere.

2.1.1 Evidence from Individuals with Aphasia from Traumatic Brain Injuries

Lenneberg (1967) compared aphasia recovery in 88 war veterans with head trauma from data compiled by Russell and Espir (1961) to a sample of 17 children aged 1–18 years old with traumatic aphasia. If the aphasia did not clear within the first three months, the war veterans exhibited permanent symptoms. Even among five patients with ‘slow and protracted improvement,’ (Lenneberg, 1967, p. 145) aphasia symptoms remained. On the contrary, children before the age of nine made complete recoveries, so long as their injuries only affected one hemisphere of the brain. Those aged nine and older recovered sufficient language abilities to hold a conversation, but with permanent aphasia symptoms that amplified with emotional tension.

2.1.2 Evidence from Language Development in Individuals with Down Syndrome

Addressing concerns that the evidence from the groups affected by aphasia from brain trauma may not be representative of individuals without brain trauma, Lenneberg (1967) offered evidence from individuals with DS. In Lenneberg et al. (1964), language development (LD) over three years was observed in 54 individuals with DS ranging from six months old to 22 years old. LD was only observed among those younger than 14. Beginning at age 14, LD stopped. Individuals ≥ 14 years old when the study began showed no LD throughout the three-year period. Lenneberg (1967) writes that the study’s results suggest that LD ceases at maturity, even in the absence of brain injury.

2.2 Krashen (1975)

Krashen (1975) published a paper examined the role of the CP in L2 acquisition, introducing a set of testable predictions for how L2 acquisition is affected by the CP. Firstly, that L2 acquisition early in life would occur through the same process as L1 acquisition before the CP, while it would require a different later in life. Secondly, that L2 acquisition before puberty occurs like L1 acquisition, but after puberty, L2 acquisition requires formal instruction. Thirdly, that L2 speakers cannot overcome foreign accents after the CP. Lastly, that only L2 speakers who began acquisition before puberty can achieve native-like competence in syntax and semantics.

Krashen suggested a potential research avenue when discussing the basis of the CPH. Noting differences in how L2 acquisition occurred between groups before and after puberty, he argued that older learners needed formal and rule-based classes to achieve competence in an L2. Citing Inhelder & Piaget's (1958) theory of cognitive development in children, he speculated that the CP coincides with the third stage of development of logical thought, the stage of formal operations. In the discussion section, I explore this hypothesis as an avenue for future research.

2.3 Johnson & Newport (1989)

The research of Johnson & Newport (1989) explored how L2 acquisition is affected by the CP. They gathered 46 native Korean and Chinese speakers, all of whom were immigrants who had been living in the United States for at least 3 years. Age of arrival (AoA) in the US was considered the participants' first exposure to the English language. AoA ranged from three to 39. The participants listened to recordings of English language sentences and were asked to judge whether the sentences were grammatically correct or not, also known as a grammaticality judgment test (GJT). In total, each participant listened to 276 sentences.

Hypothesising that the onset of the critical period began at age 15, Johnson & Newport (1989) separated the participants into two separate groups by AoA, Group 1 being between AoA 3–15 years old and Group 2 being between AoA 17–39 years of age. They found that for Group 1, there was a negative linear trend between AoA and correct GJT scores with a correlation of $R = -0.87$. This trend did not continue with Group 2. Instead, there were significantly lower GJT scores, and a correlation for the second group was $R = -0.16$.

Johnson & Newport (1989) interpreted this sharp contrast in the linear correlation between the two groups as evidence of an onset of the CP at the age of 15. As we shall see in the next section, this statistical analysis was called into question by Hakuta and Bialystok (1994) and Vanhove (2013), casting doubt on the CPH.

3 CPH Literature after 1989

3.1 Hakuta & Bialystok (1994)

Hakuta & Bialystok (1994) criticised the statistical analysis of Johnson & Newport (1989) and offered their reanalysis of their data, performing a nonlinear analysis of the trend as a function of the AoA. Around the age of 20, they noted a bend in the nonlinear trend. Dividing the data by the new CP at the

age of 20, they found that there was a linear decline with a correlation of $R = -0.87$ before the age of 20 and a second linear correlation of $R = -0.49$ after the age of 20.

Johnson & Newport (1989) were criticised for sampling. There were no checks to ensure participants had grown up with an L1 other than English. They note that childhood memory is unreliable and highly susceptible to being rewritten; those who claimed to have spoken a different L1 as a young child may have been monolingual English speakers with unreliable memories.

They argued that the strenuous nature of the test and having to listen to 278 sentences with four seconds in between sentences was an exercise in ‘mental vigor’ (Hakuta & Bialystok, 1994, p. 70), which they say would be easier for younger people due to normal aging processes.

Finally, they note that Johnson & Newport (1989) failed to account for the effect of the participants’ English language education or lack thereof on the study’s findings. Those who immigrated later would not have the support of an English education system and the advantages of ESL classes, putting them at a disadvantage compared to their younger counterparts.

3.2 Hakuta et al. (2003)

Hakuta et al. (2003) tested the CPH using United States census data for immigrant populations, allowing for a sample size of 23,000,000. They gathered data on the self-reported English levels of native Spanish and Chinese-speaking immigrants who had lived in the United States for 10 years or longer and data on the present ages and age of arrival. They tested their data for a break in the line of regression that would signify that the mean had changed at a specific point, at both the age of 15 as the CP hypothesised by Johnson & Newport (1989), and at the age of 20 from the statistical reanalysis by Hakuta & Bialystok (1994). A change in mean at either point would confirm a CP. However, Hakuta et al. (2003) found a linear decline with no break in the line of regression at either 15 or 20, meaning that there was no evidence of a CP.

3.3 DeKeyser et al. (2010)

DeKeyser et al. (2010) conducted two experiments, which tested the relationship between L2 UA and two factors, aptitude and AoA. Aptitude predicts the rate of progress of L2 learning under ideal learning conditions, according to Dörnyei (2005). Seventy-six L2 English speakers in the first study and 62 L2 Hebrew speakers for the second study, all with AoA ≥ 8 years, completed an aptitude test as well as a GJT. The first prediction was that as AoA increased, the UA of the L2 would begin to flatten, which would indicate the existence of a CP. Secondly, they predicted that aptitude would have a significant correlation with UA only among older participants.

DeKeyser et al. (2010) concluded that both predictions were supported by the resultant data. For subjects with AoA < 18 , UA correlated with AoA. For subjects with AoA between 18–40, aptitude was the predictor for UA, and among those with AoA between 50–75, neither AoA nor aptitude was a good predictor for UA. These results, they posited, would be the expected results predicted by the CPH.

Vanhove (2013) published a paper that reanalysed the DeKeyser study’s data using a regression model. They argued that the regression models ‘present the only valid alternative, provided they are fitted correctly and interpreted judiciously’ (p. 5). DeKeyser et al. (2010) concluded that their predictions had been supported by the data based on comparisons of correlation coefficients. Vanhove (2013) argued that this approach was fallacious because it conflated the correlation coefficient with slope. They asserted that DeKeyser et al.’s predictions were not supported by the data and criticised the study for weak statistical analysis.

4 Criticism of the CPH Methodology

Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) published a position paper criticising the methodology of CPH research and experimentation, arguing that the CPH cannot be properly considered a scientific hypothesis because it is unfalsifiable.

They first attack the notion that the CP ends at puberty, first proposed by Lenneberg (1967). Acknowledging that a CP ending at puberty is a testable hypothesis, there is so much variability in the ages that individuals reach puberty that a true test of this hypothesis would require finding out the individual ages at which each study participant reached puberty. A good example of this is seen in Johnson & Newport (1989), where a specific age was hypothesised to be the end of the CP. The variability in the age of puberty may have affected their result.

A second criticism is the lack of a clear, testable definition for the CP. Instead, Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) find such variability in the hypothesised CPs and results among researchers that they cannot be rightly considered to be the same hypothesis, but instead a multitude of interrelated and sometimes contradictory ones. As they note, Hawthorne et al. (2018) hypothesised that a CP for the acquisition of syntax closes at the age of 17, while Dollman et al. (2020) predict a close at the age of 9. Additional researchers (e.g., Granena & Long, 2013) hypothesise separate critical periods for lexis, syntax, and phonology. They argue that the hypotheses and findings are all so contradictory and unrelated to one another that they cannot be deemed to be one hypothesis.

Thirdly, Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) criticise the notion that experiments testing for the CP should assess the language performance of L2 speakers based on the norms of monolingual speakers. The notion of a single homogeneous standard of L1 fluency is erroneous, as native speakers vary in their mental grammar. They cite Dabrowska's (2012) research that examined individual differences in the mental grammars of monolingual speakers of Polish to show that factors like education contributed to variation in grammatical constructions.

Additionally, Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) argue that there are vital differences in the mental grammars of bilinguals and monolinguals. They suggest that a more accurate test of language skills measures the performance of L2 speakers of a given language against bilinguals who were exposed to that language from birth.

The criticisms of methodology continue with how first exposure to the L2 is determined. Since many researchers have drawn their samples from immigrant populations in countries where the L2 was the dominant language, AoA in the country where the language is dominant has been considered the speakers' first exposure to the L2 by some researchers (e.g., Johnson & Newport 1989). Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) argue that L2 speakers' socioeconomic status, educational opportunities, and the quality of L1 input are confounding variables that make AoA an unreliable measure for first exposure to the L2.

Lastly, they conclude with a discussion on statistical analysis and interpretation. As we have already demonstrated in the previous section (e.g., Vanhove, 2013; Hakuta & Bialystok, 1994), researchers can achieve contradicting results by using different statistical models on the same data set. Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) reiterate this concern in the form of a question: what counts as evidence of the CPH? The search for an answer leads to the following section on the work of Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021), two studies that Singleton & Leśniewska (2021) offer as examples of rigorous statistical analysis.

5 Contemporary Studies (2018–2021)

5.1 Hartshorne et al. (2018)

Hartshorne et al. (2018) find that there are two interrelated variables, UA and learning ability (LA), that concern researchers interested in the CPH. Studies including DeKeyser (2010) measure UA, defined as the peak language development that a speaker attains in their lifetime, as the dependent variable in experiments. LA is defined as the ability to continually gain competence in a language up to the point of perfect proficiency. According to Hartshorne et al. (2018), LA has more theoretical applicability to CPH research. LA should be expected to decrease after the CP is over.

To test this, researchers sampled 669,498 participants who spoke over 38 languages, a sample size that was at the time unrivalled by anything else in CPH literature. GJTs measured the participants' knowledge of English syntax. Analyses focused on three groups: monolinguals with L1 English, immersion learners (IL), and non-immersion learners (NIL). IL included two subcategories, simultaneous bilinguals exposed to English and another language from birth, and L2 English speakers who spent 90% of their post-exposure life (life after exposure to L2) in an English-speaking country. NI were L2 English speakers who spent a maximum of 10% of post-exposure life in an English-speaking country. A novel statistical model for testing the learning rate was used to analyse the data.

There were three distinct findings in the results. First, they found evidence that the learning rate declined by 50% by 17.4 years of age. Their analyses also produced evidence suggesting that learners who were first exposed to L2 between the ages of 10–12 were able to achieve similar levels of UA as late learners. Thirdly, their results suggested that monolingual native speakers reach UA by the time they reach 30 years old.

Returning to the question of statistical analysis, Hartshorne et al. (2018) responded to criticism by Vanhove (2013), who had argued that a sample of thousands of participants would be necessary to offer meaningful support to the CPH. As previously stated, Hartshorne et al. (2018) gathered the largest sample size in the history of CPH research.

Furthermore, Hartshorne et al. (2018) used log odds whereas previous CPH research (e.g., Johnson & Newport, 1989) used percent correct. Hartshorne et al. (2018) deemed percentage correct to be problematic because it inflates percentage differences in the results at 0% or 100%, meaning that there is more weight to a difference between 95% and 96% than there is to a difference of 50% to 51%.

Syntax acquisition was modelled using a novel computational model as a simple exponential learning process, which accounted for current age, age of first exposure, learning rate, and amount of experience. The learning rate was calculated with a piecewise function according to a sigmoid. The novel model allowed a wide range of developmental trajectories. It was fitted to the three groups, monolinguals, IL, and NIL. The model was compared against alternative statistical models but ultimately produced the best fit at $R^2 = 0.89$ with a rate change in learning rate at 17.4 years of age.

Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021) were praised for how their statistical analyses improved. After Frank (2018) questioned the results of the novel statistical model, Chen & Hartshorne (2021) responded to the critiques with a stronger model.

5.2 Chen & Hartshorne (2021)

Frank (2018) noted that Hartshorne et al. (2018) failed to provide estimates for uncertainty in any of the model parameters. Chen & Hartshorne (2021) addressed this by using bootstrapping, a statistical

procedure that resamples a single dataset into multiple simulated samples, to derive confidence intervals for parameter estimates. Frank (2018) also found that the study's measure of knowledge assumed a direct link between the portion of correct answers and the overall knowledge of a speaker. A stronger model must account for the difficulty of tasks on the test and what can be inferred from specific individuals' correct and incorrect answers. Frank proposes the use of Item Response Theory (IRT), a mathematical framework that would produce different assumptions depending on how respondents answer specific questions of varying difficulty, to avoid ceiling and floor effects. Chen & Hartshorne (2021) used IRT and designed their experiment to reduce biases related to floor and ceiling effects.

Chen & Hartshorne (2021) acknowledged that the learning rate curve was biased toward sharp drops, which could have accounted for the 50% decline in the learning rate as found by Hartshorne et al. (2018). To combat this, they produced a learning rate model that accounted for a wider range of shapes.

With all these considerations accounted for, Chen & Hartshorne (2021) retrieved data from the participants in Hartshorne et al. (2018) and added additional data from 461,903 participants who underwent the same GJT. The resultant data showed a near-perfect match with the results of Hartshorne et al. (2018), with a decline in the learning rate between the ages of 17 and 18.

6 Discussion

In this examination of the CPH literature, I have examined studies where statistical analysis was criticised (eg. Johnson & Newport, 1989; DeKeyser et al., 2010), and examples of how other researchers (Hartshorne et al., 2018; Chen & Hartshorne, 2021) met rigorous demands of statistical analysis. The collective work of Hartshorne et al. (2018), Chen & Hartshorne (2021), and Frank (2018) provides strong statistical modelling for future research.

Although Hartshorne et al. (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021) provide the strongest evidence in support of the CPH, researchers must remember that these findings only provide evidence of a decline in syntactic LA. Whether all grammatical phenomena are affected by the CP is another question to be explored. Both studies failed to acknowledge the effects of the L1 on L2 acquisition. Since only performance on English syntax was tested, future studies should test if the results remain true among speakers of other languages.

The evidence supports a CPH for syntactic acquisition. I would like to explore potential research into the cognitive mechanisms responsible for the CP for syntax. Krashen (1975) and Rosansky (1975) suggested the possibility of a causal link between Inhelder & Piaget's (1958) formal operations stage (FOS) in the development of logical thinking (DLT) and the CP for syntactic acquisition. In the following discussion, I will create a preliminary hypothesis, suggest a tentative experimental design, and explain the predicted outcomes if the hypothesis is correct.

First, I will explain Inhelder & Piaget's (1958) theory of DLT. DLT occurs in three stages, the preoperational stage (POS) occurring between ages two and seven, the concrete operational stage (COS) between ages seven and 11, and the formal operational stage (FOS) between ages 11 and 15. One experiment they conducted tested children in each stage on how they understood the law of floating bodies. This tested their ability to logically make sense of density and specific gravity, the relationship between the density of water and the density of the object.

The children were given a bucket of water and a set of objects (a wire, a needle, and a plank of wood), and asked to classify objects by whether they float or sink. Participants placed the objects in the

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water and were asked to summarise their observations and produce a general rule about floating bodies in water.

Children in POS were split into two stages, substages I-A and I-B. In I-A, children did not produce coherent classifications. In substage I-B they began to classify objects, but the classes were inconsistent and contradictory. COS subjects were also split into substages II-A and II-B. At the beginning of substage II-A, subjects categorised the objects into contradictory classes but used a reversible addition to justify contradictions. For instance, one child recognised the contradiction between his classification of a nail as being 'light', yet still sinking, saying that the object was 'iron', and all iron objects sink (p. 29). In substage II-B, children showed progress in understanding weight conservation and specific gravity. They gained a basic understanding of an object's relative 'fullness' to explain specific gravity, but their understanding of volume conservation was limited, which led to contradictory explanations for floating bodies.

The subjects in FOS demonstrated evidence of hypothetical reasoning through their consideration of multiple possibilities and their respective consequences. They identified implications and tautologies, discarding hypotheses that could not be verified. Moreover, they developed the skill to compare combinations of factors and isolate variables to understand their individual effects. They found that children in this stage began to apply abstract thinking to conceptualise and apply relationships between weight and volume.

Keeping these stages of DLT in mind, we will construct a hypothesis linking DLT and CPH. Such a hypothesis would predict that 1) if a child is first exposed to an L2 during a particular stage of DLT, they will use those logical skills to acquire syntactic knowledge, and 2) logical skills acquired during FOS interfere with the ability to acquire native-like levels of syntax, ultimately resulting in a CP. As Krashen (1975) argues, the onset of the FOS brings about a cognitive change to thinking about problems in terms of general solutions instead of specific 'ad hoc' (p. 220) solutions; the need for an explicit knowledge of the L2 grammar would inhibit the acquisition which provides us with an implicit knowledge of the L1 grammar. It is worth noting that FOS and Hartshorne et al.'s (2018) predicted cutoff age to reach native-like levels of syntax occur around the same time, with FOS occurring between ages 11 and 15, whereas the predicted cutoff age for native-like syntax is 12 years old. Equally important is the predicted age at which the learning rate declines in Hartshorne et al. (2018), between the ages of 17 and 18 years, where they argue that the critical period ends. My proposed experimental design will look for neurologically observable changes that occur at each age.

The difficulty in constructing an experiment to test this hypothesis is that the internal cognitive mechanisms are not readily accessible to a researcher observing from the outside. However, we can infer them from observations of brain activity through event-related potential (ERP) and functional magnetic resonance imagery (fMRI). My experiment will make use of both technologies to produce readings during both L2 language production use and logical tasks.

ERP patterns are brain signatures originating from groups of neurons simultaneously firing, which are measured with electroencephalography (EEG). These can answer questions about the timing of events in the brain and when they occur. DeLuca (2019) mentions in a summary of neurolinguistic research that ERP patterns of P600 are associated with morphosyntactic processing and N400 with semantic processing for L1 speakers. ERP patterns for L2 morphosyntactic processing differ from the P600, suggesting that the L2 learning process occurs differently. It is important to note, however, that the brain signatures of L2 speakers at higher proficiency levels parallel those of L1 speakers.

My hypothesis predicts similarities in ERP reading when participants perform tasks involving FOS thinking and during L2 morphosyntactic processing. If Krashen (1975) is correct about the use of FOS thought processes after the CP and the use of explicit rules to understand L2 grammar, we should

expect to observe similar readings during L2 morphosyntactic processing and tasks involving FOS thought processes for children who have reached FOS. On the other hand, ERP readings during L2 morphosyntactic processing at early stages of DLT should show differences.

ERP measures of bilingual children, separated into groups by their levels of L2 proficiency and by DLT stage, should be tested under four separate conditions, 1) at rest without any cognitive task, 2) during exposure to L1 morphosyntactic processing, 3) during L2 morphosyntactic processing, and 4) while performing a cognitive task involving formal operations. Additional categorisations will account for the previously mentioned age ranges, including the predicted cutoff to obtain native-like syntax at age 12, and the age range of 17-18 when the learning rate declines.

fMRI scans, which provide information about the location of neural activity in the brain, might provide supporting evidence that supports this hypothesis. The hypothesis predicts correlations of active brain structures on fMRI scans while a participant performs a cognitive task involving FOS thinking, and during L2 production. Several areas of the prefrontal cortex have been associated with reasoning skills (Krawczyk, 2017). Research shows that syntactic processing occurs in the left inferior frontal gyrus, inferior parietal lobule, superior temporal gyrus, middle frontal gyrus, and middle temporal gyrus (DeLuca et al. 2019). Observations of overlap would provide further evidence of a link between the processes. As above, the same considerations would be taken to measure children at different DLT stages, proficiency levels in the L2, and at the predicted age ranges for the syntax cutoff and the decline in learning rate.

If the hypothesis is correct, it will be a stepping stone toward larger findings. Further testing will be needed to establish a concrete link. Previous CPH research emphasises the necessity of statistical analysis of the data. Only with large sample sizes and improved statistical models can we form a working theory linking CPH and DLT. There is an explanatory gap between observations of brain activity and the cognitive processes which is not easily bridged, but further research may uncover neurological and cognitive bases for the CP.

7 Conclusion

At the current moment, the CPH literature for L2 acquisition is well supported by data. Critiques of methodologies provide important lessons in how future CPH research should be conducted. The main problem with CPH experiments has been statistical analysis, sample size, and unforeseen variables like aptitude which skew the results of experimentation. More recent studies from Hartshorne et al (2018) and Chen & Hartshorne (2021) have gathered strong supporting evidence for the existence of the CP, showing that the statistical shortcomings of previous studies can be overcome. Many untested hypotheses may be the key to turning the CPH into a working theory, including the untested link between CP and logical thinking development.

8 References

- Chen, T., & Hartshorne, J. (2021). More Evidence from Over 1.1 Million Subjects that the Critical Period for Syntax Closes in Late Adolescence. *Cognition*, 214, 104706.
- Dabrowska, E. (2012). Different Speakers, Different Grammars: Individual Differences in Native Language Attainment. *Linguistic Approaches to Bilingualism*, 2(3), 221-253.

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- Dekeyser, R., Alfi-Shabtay, I., & Ravid, D. (2010). Cross-Linguistic Evidence for the Nature of Age Effects in Second Language Acquisition. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, 31(4), 413-438.
- DeLuca, V., Miller, D., Pliatsikas, C., & Rothman, J. (2019). Brain Adaptations and Neurological Indices of Processing in Adult Second Language Acquisition: Challenges for the Critical Period Hypothesis. In J. Schwieter (Ed.), *The Handbook of the Neuroscience of Multilingualism* (pp. 170-196). Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The Psychology of the Language Learner*. New York: Routledge.
- Frank, M. (2018). With Great Data Comes Great (Theoretical) Opportunity. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 22(8), 669-671.
- Granena, G., & Long, M. (2013). Age of Onset, Length of Residence, Language Aptitude, and Ultimate L2 Attainment in Three Linguistic Domains. *Second Language Research*, 29(3), 311-343.
- Hakuta, K., & Bialystok, E. (1994). *In Other Words: The Science and Psychology of Second-Language Acquisition*. New York: Basic Books.
- Hakuta, K., Bialystok, E., & Wiley, E. (2003). Critical Evidence: A Test of the Critical-Period Hypothesis for Second-Language Acquisition. *Psychological Science*, 14(1), 31-38.
- Hartshorne, J., Tenenbaum, J., & Pinker, S. (2018). A Critical Period for Second Language Acquisition: Evidence from 2/3 Million English Speakers. *Cognition*, 177, 263-277.
- Inhelder, B., & Piaget, J. (1958). *The Growth of Logical Thinking from Childhood to Adolescence*. London: Routledge.
- Johnson, J., & Newport, E. (1989). Critical Period Effects in Second Language Learning: The Influence of Maturation State on the Acquisition of English as a Second Language. *Cognitive Psychology*, 21(1), 60-99.
- Kinsella, C., & Singleton, D. (2014). Much More Than Age. *Applied Linguistics*, 35(4), 441-462.
- Krashen, S. (1975). The Critical Period for Language Acquisition and its Possible Bases. *Developmental psycholinguistics and communication disorders*, 263(1), 211-224.
- Krashen, S., Long, M., & Scarcella, R. (1979). Age, Rate, and Eventual Attainment in Second Language Acquisition. *TESOL Quarterly*, 13(4), 573-582.
- Krawczyk, D. (2017). *Reasoning: The Neuroscience of How We Think*. Saint Louis: Elsevier Science & Technology.
- Lenneberg, E. (1967). *Biological Foundations of Language*. New York: Wiley.
- Lenneberg, E., Nichols, I., & Rosenberger, E. (1964). Primitive Stages of Language Development in Mongolism. *Disorders of Communication*, 42, 119-137.
- Rosansky, E. (1975). The Critical Period for the Acquisition of Language: Some Cognitive Developmental Considerations. Working Papers on Bilingualism, No. 6., from *Education Resources Information Center*: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED125256>
- Russell, W., & Espir, M. (1961). *Traumatic Aphasia*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Singleton, D., & Leśniewska, J. (2021). The Critical Period Hypothesis for L2 Acquisition: An Unfalsifiable Embarrassment? *Languages*, 6(3), 1-15.
- Vanhove, J. (2013). The Critical Period Hypothesis in Second Language Acquisition: A Statistical Critique and a Reanalysis. *PLoS ONE*, 8(7), 1-15.

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